

COMPANION IDENTITY OF THE AKIYAMA-TANIGAWA'S RELATION INVOLVING STIRLING NUMBERS

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Abstract:

We show an identity involving Stirling numbers which can be considered the companion relation of the Akiyama-Tanigawa's formula.

Key Words: Stirling Numbers, Akiyama-Tanigawa's Identity.

1. Introduction:

Akiyama-Tanigawa [1-4] obtained the identity:

$$\sum_{r=k}^n r S_n^{[r]} S_r^{(k)} = (-1)^{n+k} \binom{n}{k-1}, \quad 0 \leq k \leq n, \quad (1)$$

Where $S_m^{(j)}$ and $S_q^{[l]}$ are the Stirling numbers of the first and second kind, respectively [2, 5, 6]. Here we show the followingsimilar property [companion expression to (1)]:

$$\sum_{r=k}^n r S_n^{(r)} S_r^{[k]} = (-1)^{n+k+1} (n-k-1)! \binom{n}{k-1}, \quad 0 \leq k \leq n-1. \quad (2)$$

In Sec. 2 we prove the relation:

$$\sum_{r=k}^n x^r S_n^{(r)} S_r^{[k]} = \frac{(-1)^k n!}{k!} \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^j \binom{k}{j} \binom{jx}{n}, \quad n \geq k+1 \geq 1, \quad (3)$$

Which perhaps is known in the literature; then (3) shall permit to deduce the identity (2).

2. Proof of (3):

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^j \binom{k}{j} \binom{jx}{n} &= \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^j \binom{k}{j} \frac{1}{n!} \sum_{r=0}^n S_n^{(r)} (jx)^r, \\ &= \frac{1}{n!} \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^j \binom{k}{j} \sum_{r=0}^n S_n^{(r)} x^r \sum_{l=0}^r S_r^{[l]} l! \binom{j}{l} = \frac{(-1)^k k!}{n!} \sum_{r=k}^n S_n^{(r)} S_r^{[k]} x^r, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Where it was applied the property [5]:

$$\sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^j \binom{k}{j} \binom{j}{l} = (-1)^k \delta_{lk}, \quad (5)$$

Then (4) implies (3), *q.e.d.*

Now we apply $\frac{d}{dx}$ to (3) and after we evaluate in $x = 1$ to obtain the left member of (2):

$$\sum_{r=k}^n r S_n^{(r)} S_r^{[k]} = (-1)^{n+k+1} \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{j(n-j-1)!}{(k-j)!}, \quad (6)$$

Where it was used the relation:

$$\left[\frac{d}{dx} \binom{jx}{n} \right]_{x=1} = (-1)^{n+j+1} \frac{j(n-j-1)! j!}{n!}, \quad n \geq j+1. \quad (7)$$

From (6.34) in Gould [7] is immediate the expression:

$$\sum_{j=1}^k \frac{j(n-j-1)!}{(k-j)!} = (n-k-1)! \sum_{j=1}^k j \binom{n-j-1}{k-j} = (n-k-1)! \binom{n}{k-1}, \quad n \geq k+1 \geq 1, \quad (8)$$

Thus (8) into (6) implies (2).

This completes the proof.

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